

FDO – Granularity, Versioning, Mutability

Version 2.2

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Current and previous versions:

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Abstract

The FDO Forum needs a comprehensive definition of what a FAIR Digital Object (FDO) is and what it is not. This requires understanding the various aspects of FDOs, of which aspects of granularity and versioning are highly important. When several ESFRI¹ communities discussed the use of PIDs², the issues of granularity, versioning and mutability were broadly discussed. The results can be transferred to FDOs due to the direct relationship between PIDs and FDO. This document presents aspects that have been mentioned. The main message is that granularity needs to be defined by the community of users.

¹ European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures

² Several ESFRI and other communities started using Handles and/or DOIs to refer to data objects in their repositories.

Status of this document

This version PR 2.2 is the result of the FDO community commenting phase on version PR2.1. No further comments were made.

The WD0.1 document was a Working Draft of a recommendation track document that has been discussed in the FDO TSIG Working Group with the result of an agreed internal document published at 12. October 2021. It was based widely on a report of a broad discussion of experts in GEDE (<https://zenodo.org/record/1116189>). It has been turned now to a WD0.1 according to the document process standard to be discussed again in TSIG, before it will be offered as WD1.0 to the FDO Forum. Finally, its essentials will be extracted to be included in the FDO Specification Document.

Acknowledgments

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1. Recommendations

The granularity choices for FDOs are much aligned with what has been written so far on the choices for granularity for the assignment of PIDs which allows the FDO Forum to refer to existing recommendations that emerged in the realm of GEDE and RDA discussions.

The granularity for building FDOs is dependent on pragmatic utility decisions within communities of practice: what are useful entities to work with in the corresponding application field. Early choices can always be revised by (1) breaking up the bit-sequences of a given FDO in parts and creating new FDOs assigned to the parts or (2) by aggregating individual FDOs into collections which are also FDOs.

Data providers need to make clear policy statements whether the content of an FDO is mutable, i.e. changing over time such as often in databases, or immutable. Inspecting the correctness of these statements should be part of auditing procedures. Therefore, it is suggested to add an attribute “mutability” into the PID record.

There are different policies between communities on how to indicate versioning – some use the PID string, some use the PID record and some use extended metadata for these purposes. The choice widely depends on efficiency criteria and no general recommendation can be made except that data providers need to make clear statements on how versioning is handled.

2. Granularity

The document “Persistent identifiers: Consolidated assertions”³ released in November 2017 produced by a team of 17 experts from different research communities all active or with plans to use PIDs and accepted as an RDA Data Fabric supported document agreed on the following:

With respect to the timing of PID assignment and the issues of granularity and versioning, there are different practices across domains and PID service providers. Repositories (and other data providers) need to make clear which policies they apply, particularly with respect to the recommended timing of assignment, and the granularity needed. However, a few rules of thumb can be given, including 1) In general a DO should be assigned a PID as early as possible, at least at the time it is uploaded into a trustworthy repository; 2) In order to optimally support

³ <https://zenodo.org/record/1116189>

citations and later re-use, PIDs should in general be assigned to the smallest “chunks” of scientifically meaningful digital information (“data”) that is practical to refer to. This often translates into a high granularity, but there are many exceptions where it is desirable to assign a PID to e.g. large data sets or to collections.

As a recommendation the document makes the following statements:

PID-26. [RDA DFIG] {granularity}

PIDs are associated with collections which can consist of a number of digital entities, i.e. the level of granularity at which PIDs will be assigned is left to the communities and repositories.

Granularity is related to the smallest part of a DO that it is reasonable to refer to and/or cite and is thus connected to both collections as well as subsetting. The question of granularity is complex, and best practises are by necessity quite domain specific. There seem to be cases where a high granularity is called for, but in other situations this cannot be recommended. Use cases need to be specified by the specific community or the specific repository to provide guidance.

Note: It should be noted that early decisions about granularity can be revised by later splitting an FDO into parts, each of them being new FDOs. By forming collections which are also FDOs one can combine separate FDOs again. These two options therefore allow us to revise early decisions if they turn out to not be suitable anymore.

A few examples might illustrate practices.

2.1 Language Lexicon

In the international DOBES community it was agreed to treat the lexicon of a language as one digital object and thus assign one PID. An alternative would have been to choose the individual lexeme, which in general, is a record of descriptions for a lexical word based on a specific schema. This means that most applications use the lexicon as a whole to do some operations.

However, the problem of addressing a specific lexeme or even a specific attribute such as morphological variants needs then to be solved.

`<prefix>/<suffix>#<fragment-id>`

Assuming that the lexicon is stored in form of an XML schema-based file the answer is fairly simple: add a fragment identifier to the PID which

indicates the structure you want to access. The Handle system supports adding fragment identifiers:

<prefix>/<suffix>#<fragment-id>

The fragment id could be specified as an Xref, e.g. identifying a specific element. This allows flexible referencing - a factor important in research. People can refer to various elements without the need to first create FDOs for every lexeme, for example. For citation purposes, users simply refer to the whole lexicon **<prefix>/<suffix>**.

2.2 Media Sequences

In many research disciplines media streams stemming from observations are the basis of reasoning. Such media streams can have lengths of an hour or even more. For citation purposes it is obvious that users want to refer to the recording as a whole since it might be the recording of an interview with a politician.

However, for referencing purposes from a research paper, researchers may want to refer to a

specific moment of the recording. There are two options to do this: (1) use a fragment identifier that can be read for example by a video player or (2) cut this segment, give it a new PID and refer to the new segment. In the DOBES project the first option was chosen, since many researchers use such a

video and look for different patterns. If at each time a new segment would be created, a serious data management problem would emerge. One has to copy and adapt the metadata of the sequence and should add an attribute to the PID record referring to the sequence that says from which recording this segment was copied.

2.3 Brain Imaging

In brain imaging, recordings are often made in the form of slices. A brain image certainly is the set of all slices that belong together. The citable FDO therefore would naturally be the whole recording taken at a specific time. As in the previous examples it may be the case that a researcher annotates some patterns in a few adjacent slices. Again, two options

are possible. It could even be that a researcher creates a new collection containing only

segments that come from a variety of brain image recordings all exposing similar patterns. It is a matter of choice what is best suitable for the research purposes.

2.4 Measurement Series

Most time series data is captured in structured files with n-tuples of numbers capturing basically, for example, several variables measured at the same moments in time. These number sequences could also be stored in databases (tables). The options and challenges are similar to the above examples. Such number series could emerge from sensors that function day and night for unlimited time, i.e., the sequence of numbers would be infinite. In EUDAT it was recommended that for management and access purposes such endless streams would be cut into files where PIDs are associated to the fragments including references to the previous and subsequent fragments. Therefore, one would have a sequence of PIDs referring to each other in such a way that the sequence can be reconstructed.

With this in mind the same kind of considerations as in the above examples need to be made.

For analytic purposes either columns, rows or a set of cells may be of relevance. Again, one could extract any structure of numbers as a new FDO and assign a PID or use an appropriate fragment identifier to indicate which numbers are meant. Important as in the above cases is that there is software that understands the fragment specifications. If these number

sequences were stored in a database, the fragment identifier specification would be, e.g., an SQL statement.

2.5 Issues linked with structure of grains

In this chapter we are discussing organization variants that may have been chosen by communities for specific reasons. The FDO model is agnostic about the way content is encoded and organized. Forms of organizations have consequences on computational efficiency, of course. However, whichever organization may have been chosen, users need to take care that the context is specified in a way that the whole measurement series can be reconstructed which implies for example using time stamping.

While discussing granularity, the complexity does not only rely, as described before, in the “size” of the grain and in the ability to uniquely refer to a particular grain: challenging problems lie also in the structure of grains and how information is

organized in different structures. Let us illustrate this with an example where we assume that each measurement is associated with a time stamp.

Let us consider a scientist who is measuring the thermodynamic state of a given system: at each sampling he/she will collect a value for the temperature and a value for the pressure. This data may be simply represented as a table.

Even starting from this sample table, there are different ways for building an FDO to encapsulate the temperature/pressure set of measures. In the two following items we will give a simple example of two possible encapsulations:

In the left diagram it is indicated that the temperature series and the pressure series may be encapsulated into two different *Series-FDO*, where each FDO includes numerical vectors of values. The two resulting FDOs may be associated into a common container which will be the final *Measurement-FDO*. In the right diagram an organization is being chosen where couples of values (temperature/pressure) may be encapsulated into FDOs expressing, for example, the thermodynamic state of the system. The set of measurements will be a series of those *thermodynamic-FDOs* which again could be aggregated to a final *Measurement-FDO*. The difference between the two organizations is indicated in the following diagram.

Starting from these two different encapsulations of the same scientific information, we may easily highlight interoperability issues that users will face while interacting with data: imagine a user who will receive two different *Measurement-FDOs*, one encapsulated in the first way, the other in the second way and wants to do computations using data organized in the two different ways. The user may ask questions such as: What is the highest sensed temperature? What is then the corresponding pressure? Which FDO contains the finest series of measurements (more points)? Build a third FDO with the temperature appearing in both FDOs and highlight eventual differences in the associated pressures.

In the organization shown here, for example, whole measurement series are contained in a specific database it is obvious that such simple “textbook use-case” would be implemented

using appropriate queries. If the organizations are used as indicated above, it is obvious that such operations can only be done when time stamps and detailed metadata (column variables) specify what the FDOs contain. It is also obvious that such operations will not be efficient, since many FDOs would have to be opened in time consuming operations. Depending on the operation it may make sense to first reconstruct the complete measurement series and then carry out specific operations. These examples indicate that granularity choices need to be taken with care and eventually need to be revised to enable efficient computations.

2.6 Summary

Many concrete examples can be mentioned to illustrate granularity issues. It depends mainly on long-term access and utility considerations which will count as meaningful units to identify as FDOs and to assign a PID. These decisions need to be made by communities of practice. But it should be noted that early decisions can be overcome or corrected by referencing fragments, identifying parts, extracting them and making them FDOs or by grouping a variety of FDOs to collections and making them new collection FDOs. It should be noted that the two last operations imply careful management requirements and the possibility to split or aggregate will also be influenced by license specifications

3. Versioning & Mutability

Kahn and Wilensky already speak about mutable and immutable FDOs in their early papers⁴ and that this distinction needs to be made clear by attributes in the PID record. In addition, it makes sense that repositories clearly state what their policies are.

The PID report just cited makes the following statement:

Some repositories support specific options and functionalities. These include 1) version indicators⁵ in the attribute list or on the landing page, including support to allow machines to find and retrieve specific versions; 2) fragment indicator extensions (which are appended after the PID itself) that point to specific subsets embedded in the DO referred to; 3) embedding strings that are currently not globally resolvable (such as specific URNs) in the Handles as a suffix and thus making them resolvable; and 4) support for allowing typical life-cycle actions such as deleting, updating and splitting content. In all cases, repositories need to state clearly what their policies are.

Raw data measured by sensors or generated with the help of simulations should never be mutable, i.e. a checksum should be created and associated with the PID to prove authenticity at

⁴ R. Kahn, R. Wilensky, A framework for distributed digital object services, https://www.doi.org/topics/2006_05_02_Kahn_Framework.pdf

⁵ Adding version information to the PID (the LSID option) is not recommended.

all times. But there are many objects where the content is changing continuously as a result of growing scientific insights.

In the DOBES project on endangered languages data types such as lexicons, researcher annotations and metadata descriptions were never finished. For metadata, descriptions were often changing in small increments such as access rights specifications or names of contributors etc. It was not seen as essential to maintain old versions, i.e., metadata descriptions were modifiable FDOs with changing content but kept the same PID. Note that it does not make sense to add a checksum to the PID record of such mutable data types. It should also be noted that the “original” metadata is being used in many different ways such as by service providers that want to offer advanced services and therefore add information to the original metadata. It is not the task of the “originating” repository to take responsibility for all the copies being managed. However, improved lexicon and annotation versions that were accessible via the archive could have been used by other researchers requiring stable references. Therefore, whenever a new version was made available, a new FDO was created and a new PID was assigned.

Research communities and repositories need to define their strategies and they may differ between disciplines. Important for users but also for auditing (Core Trust Seal⁶) is that decisions are made clear and that caretakers adhere to them in a systematic way.

Practices of how to indicate versions of different type⁷ differ between communities. Some communities may use version indication in the PID string. This is not aligned with the general recommendation to not include semantics in the PID string. Some communities (such as the climate community) are using the kernel attributes to indicate previous and subsequent versions which allows for efficient navigation between versions. Other communities are using the metadata descriptions to indicate versions.

The method which is exactly being used will depend mainly on efficiency criteria. Whatever is chosen, the policy needs to be made clear.

4. Changes from previous versions

This version 0.1 has the status of a WD to be discussed in the FDO Forum. The following changes were made from the TSIG Internal version:

- The FDO Document Template was used.
- An error in chapter numbering was corrected: “3” became “2.6”

The change history of the TSIG internal document is indicated in this table:

⁶ CoreTrustSeal is a standard to assess the quality of processes of repositories (<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>)

⁷ See version of Klump et al. <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2021-012>

Version			
TSIG internal 1.0	TSIG Editing team	20.9.2011	this was edited based mainly on an ESFRI PID report also endorsed by RDA
WD0.1	CMZ	21.09.2021	Addition of paragraph 2.5 – other issues linked with granularity.
WD1.0	Editing team	17.03.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - chapter 1 has been renamed to “Recommendations” - recommendations were added - a note has been added in chapter 2 to indicate that early granularity decisions can be revised by either separating into parts or aggregating into collections - many typos were corrected and stylistic improvements were done - chapter 4 “Erata” was deleted since it not necessary anymore - a reference to Kahn& Wilensky’s paper was added - a recommendation chapter 1 was added - the term “DO” was replaced by “FDO” except for citations from earlier documents
WD2.0	Editors	7.6.2022	- approved a few language formulations and corrected a few typos
WD2.1	Editors	26.8.2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - formulations improved - 2 footnotes added
PR2.1	Editors	26.8.2022	- no further comments were made and the WD doc was transformed to a PR document
PR2.2	Editors	17.10.2022	- no further comments were made